

Pro-War Hardline Influencers in Putin's Regime in the Context of Russia's Re-Invasion of Ukraine

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Introduction

Why are the online activities of pro-war ultra-nationalist hardliners useful for Putin's regime during the re-invasion of Ukraine, despite their criticisms, such as those about the war's conduct? The regime, which seems politically stable and without significant opposition, benefits from the presence of hardliners pushing for more extreme and destructive measures, even as they criticize the government's perceived leniency on the battlefield and other aspects of the so-called 'special military operation.' How far, however, can these hardliners go in their dissent and opposition?

The regime allows such figures to criticize specific aspects of the war's execution, as well as other policies (e.g., immigration or the treatment of ethnic minorities), in exchange for their legitimizing the war and uniting against common anti-war opponents and foreign enemies. This dynamic is critical, as it explains the tensions, and even the potential for violence, between these actors and the regime, which is puzzling without a deeper understanding of the context. Nonetheless, these hardliners operate within certain informal boundaries, with the regime ready to impose harsh repression should they overstep these limits.

Some media outlets and experts suggest that by initiating the war against Ukraine, the Kremlin has unleashed ultra-nationalist hardliners, who may become difficult to control in the future. After cultivating this faction of Russian society for years, the Kremlin aims to utilize their influence for its own objectives, though this strategy may come with risks. There are claims that these hardliners could potentially threaten the stability of the political system or emerge as a new center of opposition to the regime (Kravchenko 2023; Vinokurova 2022).

This paper, however, contends that such predictions are overly speculative unless the regime faces a complete collapse. Under current conditions, ultra-nationalist pro-war hardliners lack the capacity to pose a serious challenge to the regime, particularly following Prigozhin's so-called mutiny, which was more of a failed negotiation tactic than a genuine threat. The article

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is structured as follows: first, it introduces the pro-war hardliners and their relationship with Putin's regime, then it explores the rationale behind the regime's reliance on them. The empirical section examines specific ways in which these hardliners serve the regime's interests, despite their criticisms. Finally, the discussion centers on how far these hardliners can push their criticism without overstepping the regime's boundaries.

Putin's Regime and Pro-War Hardliners

Ultra-nationalist pro-war hardliners generally align with the regime's overarching goals but often criticize it for perceived weakness, leniency, or lack of aggression, particularly in wartime. They advocate for harsher, more uncompromising policies against perceived enemies, pushing authoritarian regimes toward greater violence and repression (Stanovaya 2023; Shalunov 2022; Matthews 2022; Corcoran 2022). Unlike factions within ruling parties or state institutions, pro-war hardliners operate with a degree of autonomy, allowing them to function as both partners and critics of the regime. Pro-war hardliners in Russia draw from a mix of Russian nationalist traditions, ranging from imperialists to ethnonationalists.

Within this spectrum, some factions, such as Orthodox monarchists nostalgic for imperial Russia, conditionally support the regime (Kolstø 2014; Laryš 2023). The minority of Russian ultra-nationalists in staunch opposition to the regime is not considered part of the pro-war hardliners due to their fundamental opposition to Putin's regime. The split among ultra-nationalists—between loyalists, conditional supporters, and staunch opponents—intensified following the start of Russia's war in Ukraine in 2014. While anti-regime nationalists largely opposed the war—sometimes even siding with Ukraine—pro-war hardliners remained aligned with the Kremlin's imperialist agenda (Horvath 2015; Laruelle 2018; Laryš 2023). Since 2014, Putin's regime has maintained a complex relationship with pro-war hardliners.

Russian authorities have at times delegated key tasks to these actors, particularly during the annexation of Crimea and the outbreak of war in Donbas, such as Igor Girkin, who played a pivotal role in igniting the conflict, invading Sloviansk with his militia in April 2014. These hardliners helped mobilize anti-Ukrainian sentiment and coordinated pro-Russian activities (Horvath 2021; Likhachev 2016). Over time, the ideological positions of Putin's regime and ultra-nationalist hardliners have increasingly converged, as the Kremlin has leaned into nationalist and imperialist narratives. Pro-war hardliners share core ideological beliefs with the regime, including anti-Western resentment, the perception of Russia as a unique and supreme state-civilization, statism, militarism, autocracy, and disdain for Western values (Laruelle 2023;

Kolesnikov 2023; Oksamytna 2023; Tolz and Hutchings 2023; Snegovaya, Kimmage, and McGlynn 2023). While they reinforce Russia's imperial identity, mythology, and geopolitical imagination, pro-war hardliners tend to be more extreme in their views, particularly regarding immigration, ethnic nationalism, and anti-Semitism.

Unlike the regime, which rejects ethnonationalism as a destabilizing force, many hardliners accuse Russian officials of cowardice or even complicity in facilitating immigration from non-Slavic countries and enabling "ethnic criminality" (Laruelle 2023; Verkhovskiy 2023; Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 19 July 2022). For instance, the Sons of Monarchy Telegram channel laments that "while fathers are liberating Novorossiia from Ukrainian Nazism, their sons are being harassed and prosecuted for fighting back against ethnobandits" (Syny monarchii, 9 February 2023). Similarly, migrants are described as "locusts that attack the rear of our country while people are fighting on the front lines" (Govorit TopaZ, 19 May 2023).

Following Russia's re-invasion of Ukraine in 2022, pro-war hardliners became increasingly relevant in public space and vocal in their criticism of state officials and military leaders, blaming them for indecisiveness, incompetence, and corruption that, in their view, sabotaged the expected blitzkrieg (Hovorun 2023). Unlike other dissenting voices, which were swiftly silenced, Putin permitted pro-war figures to openly criticize officials (Dalton 2023). Frustrated by the government's perceived leniency, these hardliners called for more radical measures, including the complete conquest of Ukraine, martial law, and mass mobilization (Kruglova 2023; Kravchenko 2023). This dynamic has fueled speculation over whether they could destabilize Putin's regime or pose its most significant internal challenge (Oliphant and Vasilyeva 2022; Matthews 2022; Shalunov 2022).

The Role of Hardliners in Putin's Regime Amid the Ongoing War Against Ukraine

I argue that despite their criticism, pro-war hardliners are useful to the regime as they legitimize the war by portraying it as both necessary and honorable, and mobilize against external and internal enemies that could undermine the regime and discredit the war efforts. Putin has accommodated the hardliner community, recognizing their value to the regime as key figures in the information space who reinforce the narrative of achieving victory in Ukraine at any cost (Bugayova 2022). The regime likely views it as relatively safe to allow hardliners to mobilize in the online space, as their challenges do not threaten the regime's legitimacy in the way that anti-war dissenters might (Fediunin 2022). Additionally, some experts contend that

Putin's regime is not capable of sustaining ideological mobilization for the war on its own (Savin 2023).

Since February 2022, there has been a marked increase in state intervention into the private life of citizens that often take the form of calls for displays of patriotism from the population. Patriotism has evolved into an imposed framework that has grown increasingly restrictive over time. As a result, the regime has not only claimed patriotism as its own but has also mandated it for all citizens, expanding its control across various spheres (Komin 2024). Within this context, pro-war hardliners function as voluntary auxiliary forces, reinforcing militarism and state-defined patriotism amid widespread societal conformism (Kolesnikov 2024; Volkov and Kolesnikov 2023).

In Russia, individuals are largely preoccupied with their personal interests, leading to widespread disengagement from the public sphere. People focus on preserving their achievements and improving their living conditions, while the war and the regime's growing authoritarianism barely register unless they are directly affected. The population appears detached from the reality of the war, not out of apathy, but as a pragmatic response to a fragmented society incapable of uniting around any common cause—whether in opposition to the war or in support of government policies (Inozemtsev 2024; Chuarshin 2024). For most Russians, the war with Ukraine has long receded into the backdrop of daily life (Tenisheva 2024).

Hardliners frequently criticize their compatriots for lacking patriotism and prioritizing material comfort over the "defense of the motherland" (Makarychev and Medvedev 2024). Feeling betrayed, they lament that ordinary Russians refuse to sacrifice, fight, or die for the cause (Loginova 2024). They condemn the population's passivity, accusing citizens of being disengaged, uninvolved, and merely "Russian in name only." Hardliners also direct their frustration at the regime, blaming it for fostering a society of extreme individualists and consumers who remain detached from the war. The Soldatskaya Pravda Telegram channel, run by Mikhail Polynkov, expressed this sentiment, stating: "90% of the Russian Federation's population is not involved in the war. They are under the spell of lulling propaganda—lost in an alcoholic haze, under anesthesia. This situation has been deliberately created and encouraged by the 'cunning-plan' regime: 'Everything is fine, the army has everything it needs, nothing is required'" (Soldatskaya Pravda, 14 August 2024).

According to opinion polls, 76% of Russians express support for the actions of the Russian military in Ukraine. However, only 36% favor continuing hostilities, while 55% believe it is time to engage in peace negotiations with Ukraine (Levada-tsentr 2025). In contrast,

pro-war hardliners fiercely oppose any peace agreements unless the objectives of the so-called "special military operation"—however they are defined—are fully achieved. They reject what they perceive as a “backroom deal” (*dogovorniyak*) with the enemy, viewing it as betrayal. Hardliners have voiced their resistance across Telegram channels, equating negotiations with defeat:

- "Any backroom deal—consider it betrayal" (Trinadtsatyi, 27 November 2023).
- "We are personally against any kind of 'backroom deals'; we support ending the war with peace on Russia's terms and Ukraine's capitulation. Is there any other way?" (PriZrak Novorossii, 10 February 2025).
- "Any backroom deal NOW would be a severe defeat for Russia" (Soldatskaya pravda, 6. November 2024).
- "Our great ancestors ended wars with complete victory, not backroom deals" (Syny monarkhii, 9 August 2024).
- “Yes! War. Because I do not need peace with traitors, political prostitutes, perverts, enemies of my people, enemies of my Motherland, and opponents of everything that is dear and important to me. I see no other way to resolve the conflict with them except through total destruction!” (Govorit TopaZ, 21 February 2025).

Hardliners’ criticism, particularly that one concerning negligence and embezzlement related to military needs, is sensitive as may challenge the very foundations of a regime built on corruption—criticized by hardliners "for the sake of Russia." Such critiques can undermine the regime's legitimacy and should be managed through measures like violence, bans, and repression, even against those who are ostensibly loyal. The mechanisms for regulating these potential conflicts are opaque, unregulated, and unpredictable, tied to the internal dynamics of Putin’s regime, which establishes the limits of how far hardliners can criticize. The regime is guided by unwritten informal rules known as "understandings" (*“ponyatiya”*)—a defining feature of Putin’s power structure (Idov 2017).

This system functions outside formal constitutional institutions, governed by its own set of rules and practices, forming what can be described as an ‘informal constitution’ (Sakwa 2020; Dawisha 2014, 38). In Russia's political and bureaucratic spheres, these understandings often take precedence over formal laws, regulating socio-political interactions and relying on force, violence, and patrimonial logic as primary sources of authority (Domańska 2014). These ‘understandings’ can shift unpredictably, requiring insiders and outsiders alike to sense or guess their boundaries, effectively substituting for formal law (Reddaway 2018, 7).

Relevance of Pro-War Hardline Influencers in Russian Public Space

Identifying the influence of pro-war hardliners and other actors in autocratic regimes is inherently challenging, as claims regarding their impact on policymaking are difficult to verify. In authoritarian systems, including Russia, the opacity of decision-making processes makes it particularly hard to trace how policies are shaped. Furthermore, authoritarian leaders may preemptively account for the potential preferences or reactions of some specific actors, even in the absence of explicit pressure. This anticipatory behavior further complicates efforts to infer direct political influence of pro-war hardliners in current Russia.

Pro-war hardliners have become influential voices in the public sphere following Russia's re-invasion of Ukraine, which has drastically elevated their public profile and brought them hundreds of thousands of new followers in the regime devoid of political competition (Laruelle 2023; Makarychev and Medvedev 2024, 120; BBC News 2023; Wenger 2022). Hardline groups in social media primarily function as digital echo chambers, reinforcing their own views within a fragmented and largely conformist society. However, assessing the extent to which hardline pro-war rhetoric has influenced public opinion on the war and support for wartime policies—such as expanded military training in secondary schools—is nearly impossible.

No opinion polls in Russia specifically measure the influence of hardliners on public attitudes toward the war. Even if such surveys existed, isolating their impact from the pervasive influence of state-run pro-war propaganda in TV—trusted by over 50% of the population (Kuzichkin 2024)—would be extremely difficult. Television remains the primary source of pro-war messaging for older Russians, while younger generations rely more on Telegram and other social media platforms, making information consumption highly generational (BBC 2023). Older individuals are also significantly more likely to support the so-called "special military operation," whereas Telegram, which skews younger, offers a more diverse media landscape by hosting both pro-Kremlin and opposition channels (Alyukov, Kunilovskaya, and Semenov 2022).

Regarding the support for the war against Ukraine among Russian Telegram users, there is no specific data available. However, Telegram has become a key tool for spreading pro-regime military propaganda. The availability of the currently non-existent data on the percentage of people who trust social media as their main source of information while maintaining a pro-war stance and the number of pro-war users of Telegram could become key indicators of the success of hardline influencers, although there can be more reasons for the

higher number of social media users and war support among them. Compared to other Russian social media platforms like Odnoklassniki or VK, Telegram remains more diverse, accommodating both pro-regime and anti-regime voices (Alyukov, Kunilovskaya, and Semenov 2022).

Thus, Telegram, as increasingly popular social media platform since February 2022, is relevant as a battlefield for younger people with anti-war positions and as echo chamber for people skeptical of official propaganda but sharing pro-war stances. Hardliners' messages create alternative channels for pro-war sentiment to circulate as they represent a vocal part of the pro-war but critical part of society (Erpyleva 2022; McGlynn 2023; Fediunin 2022; Sauer 2022). That segment of pro-war society is estimated by various sources to be around 10-15% of the Russian population (RBK 2023; Laruelle 2023; Kappinen and Zhuravlev 2023; Loginova 2024). Although small, this segment could be crucial if Putin's regime faces danger. This active segment also broadly participates in social media, displaying warmongering (Garner 2023).

Case Selection, Methods and Data Collection

Pro-war hardliners lack a strict organizational structure and a specific ideology, though both elements are developing: informational networks (primarily Telegram), fundraising for the Russian army, and promoting uncritical patriotism and aggressive militarism rooted in imperialism and nationalism (Danilov 2023). I selected popular pro-war hardliners with large following (dozens of thousands) as representative samples within the vibrant pro-war circles that have operated with a degree of autonomy from the regime (Fediunin 2022; Kruglova 2023). Despite lacking formal leadership, two informal figures emerged as prominent pro-war hardliners from February 2022 until the summer of 2023: Igor Girkin, who initiated the war in eastern Ukraine in April 2014, and Yevgeniy Prigozhin, who led the notorious Wagner Group until his death in August 2023 (Dalton 2023; Kravchenko 2023).

I selected 12 Telegram channels (see Table 1) run by pro-war hardliners and categorized them into three subgroups based on their social ties within various hardline pro-war networks. These networks include figures affiliated with the Wagner Group, Donbas rebel militias, and Orthodox monarchist thinkers—who represent an ideological middle ground between staunchly loyal nationalists and the uncompromising ultra-nationalist opposition. These channels were chosen for their connections to the most influential hardliners—Prigozhin and Girkin—who played key strategic and ideological roles in the war against Ukraine in 2014 and after 2022.

Additionally, they were selected for their prominence. While they are not the most widely followed pro-war influencers (such as Yuriy Podolyaka or Rybar, who each have over a million followers), they are among the most significant Telegram channels within the autonomous hardliner sphere that remains critical of the regime. In contrast, the most popular pro-war bloggers and correspondents—despite their large followings—tend to focus narrowly on military matters, lack a broader political agenda, and cannot truly be classified as hardliners, as they do not exercise independent agency. The sharp rise in the popularity of these hardline channels since the re-invasion of Ukraine highlights Telegram’s growing influence, particularly in discussions about the war. While not all of their followers necessarily support their views, this does not diminish the increasing relevance of these actors in Russia’s online public sphere since 2022.

Table 1. Selected Ultra-Nationalist TG Channels and Number of Subscribers

Telegram Channel	25 Feb. 2021	25 Feb. 2022	25 Feb. 2023	25 Feb. 2024	25 Feb. 2025
Former Pro-Wagner Group “Network”					
Vladlen Tatarskiy (Maxim Fomin)	12,316	44,523	552,397	300,788	229,989
Govorit TopaZ (Evgeniy Rasskazov)	5,180	8,160	56,776	121,282	149,273
DShRG Rusich	-	-	55,922	159,139	252,293
Trinadsatyi (Egor Guzenko)*	-	-	95,603	225,811	270,265
Novorossiia 2014 “Network”					
Strelkov Igor Ivanovich (Igor Girkin)	9,611	35,151	802,207	517,123	405,848
Ryadovoi Gubarev (Pavel Gubarev)	829	972	51,021	35,434	30,921
PriZrak Novorossii (Vladimir Grubnik)**	-	8,122	172,358	190,198	195,803
Soldatskaya pravda (Mikhail Polynkov)***	-	-	-	17,013	52,796
Orthodox-Monarchist “Network”					
Syny monarkhii	7,958	14,630	38,614	50,365	74,952
Obyknovennyi tsarizm****	-	4	24,737	34,205	39,585
Pod led	3,700	6,901	17,245	22,503	26,624
Kholmogorov	6,190	11,316	41,254	36,840	8,980

(Source: <https://tgstat.ru/>)

* Channel was founded on April 13, 2022.

** Channel was founded on August 3, 2021

*** Channel was founded on August 30, 2023

**** Channel was founded on February 24, 2022.

The first ‘network’ centers around the former Wagner Group, which operated as an autonomous combat force outside the Russian military while maintaining an ambiguous relationship with the state (Marten 2019). Rather than analyzing Prigozhin’s social media presence as an influencer, I consider him a symbolic figure—an outspoken advocate of ultra-nationalist “patriotic dissent” and a unifying force for influencers who either worked for him, received financial backing from him, or aligned themselves with Wagner Group (Muzhayev 2023;

Kruglova 2023; Dalton 2023; Shalunov 2022). The hardliners selected from this network include Wagner supporters, such as DShRG Rusich—a reconnaissance and assault unit led by neo-Nazi Aleksei Milchakov—as well as figures like Evgeniy Rasskazov (formerly linked to Rusich but later defecting to the *Espanola* military unit formed by Russian football hooligans), Vladlen Tatarsky (Maksim Fomin) from Donetsk, whose Telegram channel remains active despite his assassination in April 2023, and Egor Guzenko, who runs the channel *Trinadtsatyi* (Thirteenth).

The second network revolved around Igor Girkin (Strelkov), a key figure in the 2014 war in Donbas and a self-proclaimed icon of the "Russian Spring." Since the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022, he has been at odds with Prigozhin. Members of this network were primarily associated with the vision of "Novorossiia"—a historical term repurposed as a nationalist project to encompass much of eastern and southern Ukraine (Corcoran 2022). Novorossiia became a rallying point for pro-war hardliners who traveled to eastern Ukraine in 2014, hoping to create their idealized state (Plokhly 2023). Girkin, a staunch nostalgist for Tsarist Russia, has repeatedly attempted—unsuccessfully—to establish ultra-nationalist movements in Russia. His latest initiative, the now-defunct Angry Patriots Club ("*Klub rasserzhennykh patriotov*"), was an informal pro-war movement that criticized what it perceived as the Kremlin's overly cautious approach to the war (Bailey, Wolkov, Hird, and Clark 2023). This network included long-time pro-war activists such as Pavel Gubarev from Donetsk, Vladimir Grubnik from Odesa—who runs the Telegram channel *PriZrak Novorossii* (The Ghost of Novorossiia)—and Mikhail Polynkov, Girkin's recruiter in the Donbas in 2014, who operates the *Soldatskaya Pravda* (Soldier's Truth) channel.

The third group consists of Orthodox monarchist ideologists and publicists who, unlike the previous two networks, have not actively participated in combat since 2014 or 2022. However, they play an important role in shaping the ideological landscape of Russian ultra-nationalism and in providing ideological justification for the war. Unlike regime-aligned ideologues such as Aleksandr Dugin or Aleksandr Prokhanov, these figures retain a degree of independence while commanding substantial followings, with tens of thousands of subscribers on Telegram. The most prominent among them include the Ordinary Tsarism ("*Obyknovennyi tsarizm*") channel, co-founded by ultra-nationalist publicists Egor Kholmogorov, Artemiy Sych, and Svyat Pavlov, as well as the Sons of Monarchy ("*Syny monarkhii*") channel, administered by ultra-nationalist publicist and blogger Roman Antonovskiy, who is closely associated with Malofeyev's Tsargrad media (Britskaya and Prokushev 2023).

Content Analysis of Selected TG Channels

I compiled a dataset from 12 Telegram (TG) channels (see Table 1), selecting 100 posts from each, resulting in a total of 1,200 posts as a representative sample for qualitative analysis. The posts were manually collected and categorized based on narratives related to hardliners' promotion of patriotism and militarism, as well as their relationship with the regime in the context of the war. The dataset was first analyzed through open coding to identify recurring patterns, key terms, and messages within the social media content. This process revealed that pro-war hardliners' TG channels employ militarist and ultra-patriotic rhetoric to justify the war, including the glorification of Russian soldiers, the cult of violence and masculinity, recruitment efforts, fundraising appeals, and the legitimization of the war. Additionally, they engage in dehumanizing the enemy, attacking the anti-war opposition, and criticizing both society for its perceived lack of enthusiasm and officials for corruption, weakness, or even treason. Following open coding, axial coding was used to identify deeper connections between these narratives by clustering related themes into broader analytical categories.

Three interrelated categories emerged: (1) the endorsement of militarist values deemed essential for sustaining the war effort; (2) the legitimization of the war against Ukraine, portraying it as necessary, justified, existential, and inevitable; and (3) the identification of key adversaries, including the "collective West," Ukraine, domestic opponents of the war, and even those perceived as insufficiently enthusiastic about it. These narratives align closely with the Kremlin's broader war legitimization strategy, reinforcing the regime's messaging while maintaining a degree of autonomy. Through selective coding, these findings coalesced into a central theme: pro-war hardliners' uncompromising support for the war as a core element of their broader, yet conditional, backing of Putin's regime. By amplifying these narratives, hardliners appeal to the segment of Russian society that supports the war but remains skeptical of state-controlled television propaganda, thereby exerting influence within their own ideological sphere.

I examine both the actions and discourses of pro-war hardliners, considering them as architects of narratives expressed through their public statements, particularly on social media platforms like Telegram. Social media has provided hardliners in authoritarian regimes with a new avenue for influence, reducing their reliance on state-controlled media. Despite many social media platforms being blocked in Russia, Telegram has more than doubled in size since the re-invasion, emerging as a key platform for information warfare (Wenger 2022). Social media are an important part of Russia's authoritarian media ecology (Alyukov, Kunilovskaya,

and Semenov 2022). Telegram remains one of the few social media channels not yet banned or classified as extremist in Russia (Pankratova 2022). By January 2023, the number of daily users of Telegram in Russia had increased to 48 million, compared to 25.5 million by January 2022, representing 40% of the country's entire Internet audience. By May 2023, 51.2 million Russians were using Telegram, accounting for 42% of the Internet audience in the country (Pertsev 2023).

In Table 1, we can observe that the audience of TG channels—excluding those whose authors are dead or imprisoned (such as Vladlen Tatarsky and Igor Girkin)—is generally increasing rather than declining. To illustrate the long-term trends in their popularity and relevance, I included data spanning back to February 2021, one year before the re-invasion of Ukraine. This allows for a clearer comparison of follower growth over time, highlighting how these channels gained traction with the onset of the war and, in many cases, continue to expand their reach. It is important to note that not all followers necessarily share the views expressed in these channels, yet their rising numbers indicate sustained engagement and influence within the hardline pro-war sphere. I conducted a content analysis of all the Telegram channels listed in Table 1 from February 25, 2021, to February 25, 2025.

Value of Pro-War Hardliners' Activities for Putin's Regime

Pro-war hardliners voluntarily assisted in mobilizing for the war against Ukraine in 2014-2015 and have been essential since the re-invasion in 2022 for purposes such as promoting militarist values, explaining the necessity and 'inevitability' of the war and mobilizing against common external and domestic enemies that altogether legitimizes regime's war against Ukraine. Winning the war against the "collective West" in Ukraine requires putting Russian society in a war mood (Laruelle 2023). Using the dataset, I analyzed three key categories: the endorsement of militarist values, the legitimization of the war, and the mobilization against key enemies.

Endorsement of Militarist Values

A dominant theme across selected TG posts is the glorification of violence and heroism, often centered on the actions of Russian soldiers. These posts celebrate their bravery and sacrifice, depicting them as the ultimate embodiments of heroism, loyalty, and patriotism. The use of heroic imagery—referring to soldiers as "heroes of Russia" and "defenders of the Motherland"—elevates their actions to the realm of national mythology (see Syny monarchii,

24 August 2023). The language constructs a narrative of unwavering courage in the face of adversity: "Right now, our task is to achieve our own Victory, despite all obstacles—not only external but, unfortunately, internal as well" (Strelkov Ivan Ivanovich, 9 May 2024).

Beyond glorification, many posts actively encourage readers to participate in the war effort—whether by enlisting, supporting soldiers, or spreading propaganda. Drawing historical parallels with past military conflicts, they emphasize a sense of duty and inevitability, calling for total mobilization. The war is framed as a national struggle requiring unity and sacrifice, with business leaders and civilians urged to contribute financially or materially (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 22 September 2022). Some posts even advocate for a full-scale societal transformation, arguing that sustaining the war effort demands sweeping economic, military, and social restructuring (PriZrak Novorossii, 6 September 2024).

These narratives reinforce a nationalist message that war is not merely a political necessity but an opportunity to affirm Russia's greatness through individual acts of valor. The framing of war as central to Russian identity is evident, particularly in the way figures like Yevgeny Prigozhin, the leader of the Wagner Group, are elevated to heroic status. Several posts pay tribute to his leadership and battlefield prowess: "Under their command, our warriors struck the enemy and captured cities in hard and often unequal battles. Yevgeny Viktorovich and Dmitry Valeryevich [Utkin] led PMC Wagner through all storms and hardships, through relentless effort forging the best assault infantry in the world. They proved that where Wagner is, there is victory" (Trinadtsatyi, 23 August 2024).

Wagner Group is displayed as one of the most relevant examples of the promotion of uncompromising warrior culture, contrasting it with Western liberalism and humanism (Dalton 2023). It created a new brand of ultra-violence and hypermasculine aesthetics (Cherta 2023). Wagner Group's ultra-violent image peaked in November 2022 when a video of an alleged traitor being killed with a sledgehammer was posted by the Wagner Group-affiliated TG channel Grey Zone (Medvedev 2023). Egor Guzenko (Trinadtsatyi) was photographed several times on his TG channel with a sledgehammer engraved with the Wagner logo and the text: "Fear nothing, believe in your path, follow your goal." (Trinadtsatyi, 30 October 2023). After his death, Prigozhin became a cult figure among some Russian teenagers who admire his supposed candor (Smorodinov 2024).

The notion that Russia is "saving the world" and fulfilling a historic mission is a recurring theme. The channels frequently reinforce the idea of absolute victory, with phrases like "until total victory" emphasizing a refusal to accept any negotiated settlement or compromise. Statements such as "War is in the genetic memory of Russians [...] We are

destined for Victory!" (Vladlen Tatarskiy, 21 September 2022) and "We are ready to go until the end. We want Victory" (Trinadtsatyi, 22 January 2025) underscore an unwavering commitment to triumph. The rhetoric portrays war as an existential struggle, leaving no space for diplomacy or retreat, and calls for total mobilization, such as "If we want to end this war with victory, we must fight totally, massively, and effectively. We must abandon all rotten illusions, false hopes, and magical thinking that things will somehow resolve themselves. They won't. 'Our guys' won't come—because we are all we have" (PriZrak Novorossii, 23 January 2025).

The language of "victory at any cost" fosters a sense of inevitability and total commitment. A prominent theme in these TG posts is the glorification of war, not merely as a political necessity but as a sacred and historical duty. For example, one post asserts that the "Heart of the Warrior" understands that death is an illusion, and embracing this truth transforms individuals into true warriors (Ryadovoi Gubarev, 23 January 2025). This narrative is further strengthened through references to revered Russian historical figures such as Alexander Nevsky and Dmitry Donskoy, portraying the war against Ukraine as a continuation of Russia's centuries-old defense of its sacred lands (Vladlen Tatarskiy, 27 February 2023). By idealizing warriors who fight for the "Russian World," these messages infuse the war effort with religious and mythic significance.

Supporting militarist values is beneficial for the regime because Putin's regime is promoting aggressive militarism in the Russian society, especially since 2014 after the annexation of Crimea. State institutions such as schools, the military, the media, and the Orthodox Church, promotes the idea that Russia is besieged by external enemies and an internal "fifth column." The regime's propaganda champions "traditional" and "patriotic" values, which pro-war hardliners echo and amplify (Snegovaya, Kimmage, and McGlynn 2023; Kolesnikov 2024; McGlynn 2023). Putin's regime also cultivates the cult of heroism, sacrifice and glorious 'patriotic' death in the war that is not mourned but rather celebrated (Makarychev and Medvedev 2024; Garner 2023). Pro-war hardliners help the regime to promote militarist values crucial to the state's war efforts, offering Russians the chance to die "for the Motherland" instead of a hopeless, impoverished life (Verstka 2023).

Promotion of War's Legitimacy, Necessity, and Inevitability

A dominant theme in the selected TG posts is the portrayal of the war as a historical necessity for Russia's survival as the existential struggle against its mortal enemies. "It's not about

whether we want it [the war against Ukraine] or not. It's about the fact that it is necessary—a total people's liberation war" (PriZrak Novorossii, 15 April 2022). TG posts frequently present Russia's actions as defensive measures against Western aggression. Ukraine is framed as a puppet of Western powers, and the conflict is portrayed as a struggle for Russian sovereignty. Some posts argue that Ukraine is an artificial construct created by the West to undermine Russia, reinforcing a narrative that delegitimizes Ukrainian national identity. The war is framed as a continuation of previous struggles, particularly against Western hegemony, NATO, and "Ukrainian Nazism": "The Russian army is now changing not only the future of Russia and Ukraine. The Russian army is changing the entire world order that emerged after the USSR's defeat in the Cold War" (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 25 February 2022).

This narrative aligns with the belief that Ukraine must be completely defeated and integrated into Russia to prevent future conflicts. Many posts explicitly state that Russia's war goal should not be limited to territorial gains but must involve the complete eradication of Ukrainian statehood (Pod Led, 24 February 2022). Girkin shared: "Fact that the Kremlin refuses to understand and accept [is that] the so-called "Ukraine" must be destroyed as a state—completely. Otherwise, it will destroy Russia" (Strelkov Ivan Ivanovich, 9 June 2023). Ukraine is described as an "anti-Russian" project that must be dismantled for Russia to secure its future: "The only truly valid objective of the special military operation might be the destruction of Ukraine as a state. The liberation of Little Russia and Novorossia from the Ukrainian delusion. Complete Russification of these territories" (Syny monarchii, 14 January 2023). Another TG channel posted: "The anti-Russian project "Ukraine" is designed solely and exclusively for conflict with Russia—a deadly conflict" (Soldatskaya prava, 31 January 2025).

It demonstrates that necessity of the war is closely tied to anti-Ukrainian rhetoric. The most extreme posts use dehumanizing language to describe Ukrainians, referring to them with slurs and advocating for their complete destruction. Pro-war hardliners either advocate sheer genocide, viewing Ukrainians as subhuman with no right to live "on Russian lands" or cultural genocide, or frames Russia as a savior, capable of rescuing Ukraine from the West's "decadent temptations" and "neo-Nazism" and "Russophobia" imposed by the Ukrainian authorities (Pynnöniemi and Parpei 2024).

Yegor Kholmogorov posted that "every Ukrainian must be killed. There shouldn't be any Ukrainians. I'm sure most unhappy Russians will find the strength to kill the Ukrainian in themselves. We will help the rest of them" (Kholmogorov, 22 August 2022). The Rusich's Telegram channel consistently called for the total annihilation of Ukrainians although some posts have been later deleted by channels' administrator(s). One post advocated for the killing

of all Ukrainians—regardless of age or gender—arguing that children would grow up to avenge their parents (DShRG Rusich, 5 August 2023). Another stated, "We need to kill as many Ukrainians as possible, regardless of gender or age, in order to live peacefully at home and in the liberated territories" (DShRG Rusich, 2 April 2023).

A significant number of posts depict Ukrainians as brainwashed by Western ideology, portraying them as enemies that need to be "saved" from their own national identity: "There are Russians in these lands who are raised as Ukrainians, and as a result, they become the very people we are fighting against" (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 4 April 2023). The resistance to Russia's re-invasion by Ukrainians has convinced many pro-war hardliners that the 'virus of fascism' is deeply embedded in Ukrainian society, necessitating genocidal measures against this 'existential threat' to Russian identity and civilization (Dudko 2022; Ioffe 2023).

Promotion of war's legitimacy, necessity, and inevitability is beneficial for Putin's regime because it provides pro-war ideological motives, contents, and explanations why the war is essential and worth fighting (Fediunin 2022). Pro-war hardliners see war as an integral part of the nation's identity. Some experts suggest the regime lacks a clear explanation for why the war started (Savin 2023). To the hardliners, the survival and restoration of Russia's greatness depend on this war. They believe they are fighting a final, spiritual battle against anti-Russian forces (Garner 2023). The TG channels disseminate ahistorical and quasi-religious narratives and imagery to support the mission to eliminate the enemy and reclaim a lost empire. For the pro-war hardliners, the war against Ukraine is a "holy war" (Mitrokhin 2024).

Mobilization Against Common External and Internal Enemies

As Putin's regime becomes more paranoid, traitors are seen everywhere, undermining the war effort (Garner 2023). Pro-war hardliners are willing partners in exposing 'traitors' and 'enemies' within, engaging in both offline and online pro-regime vigilantism. They continually seek objects for hatred, targeting alleged Western-funded, anti-Russian conspiracies (Garner 2023). Prigozhin was involved in fighting the opposition after 2011-2012 protests, creating troll factories to fabricate support for the regime. He benefited from the regime's strategy of employing proxies to target domestic anti-war opposition and to project an illusion of widespread public support for the war (Horvath and Currie 2023).

Such strategy was linked to hatred toward those who left "our" group and joined a different one that has been applied toward Ukrainians and domestically against those called "liberasts" (a derogative combination of "liberal" and "pederast") and "foreign agents". These

humiliating labels are not simply language games but work to dehumanize opponents and prepare for their radical exclusion and domestic purification of Russian nationhood from those ‘alien elements’ (Makarychev and Makarychev 2024, 31-35). Liberals, pacifists, Ukrainians, and LGBTQ+ individuals are frequently lumped together by hardliners as a singular enemy force undermining Russian society that are allegedly present even among the regime’s officials.

The selected TG posts employ dehumanizing language to describe external (Ukrainians) and domestic enemies (liberals, political dissidents, anti-war societal segment). Pro-war hardliners justify aggressive actions against them. Some messages directly encourage their audience to take action, such as removing pacifist posters or harassing perceived traitors, for instance: “We urge all readers to cleanse Russian cities of pacifist garbage” (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 28 February 2022). Pacifists are portrayed as complicit in supporting "Nazism" in Ukraine. Liberal opposition figures and Western influences are framed as existential threats to Russia. The idea that the liberal opposition supports Ukraine, calling them “zaukraintsy,” is a recurring theme, reinforcing a "traitor within" narrative (Vladlen Tatarsky, 26 October 2022).

There are attacks on cultural figures like comedians and musicians, accusing them of spreading Western decadence and anti-Russian sentiments: “After February 24, the "liberal opposition" openly admitted its hatred for Russia and Russians” (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 17 August 2022). Pro-regime hardliners actively target individuals labeled as "Russophobes" for expressing anti-war sentiments and artists who have not shown support for Russia’s re-invasion. Instead of rallies and street violence, ultra-nationalist pro-war hardliners engage in online harassment of the undesirable, and involved their followers in these activities. Mass mailing of threats and compromising information, writing complaints and denunciations to law enforcement agencies and social media administrations, dislikes and negative comments - all of this has become in recent years familiar and popular methods of their work (Alperovich 2024a).

For example, TG channel Sons of Monarchy singled out theater director Yevgenia Berkovich as well as comedian Ruslan Belyi, who “betrayed his country after the start of the SVO [“special military operation”]. He left Russia and spoke out against the SVO in support of Ukraine. [...] We desperately need a law to ensure that all opponents of Russia and the SVO can no longer earn a penny in our country. Being a Russophobe should be a sad, painful, and poor choice. Or better yet, deadly” (Syny monarkhii, 2 May 2023; 9 July 2024).

As an illustration, pro-war hardliners also fought against a monument to Odesa-born satirist Mikhail Zhvanetskiy in Rostov-on-Don, calling him a ‘Russophobe’ for his reportedly pro-Ukrainian position: “By the way, a memorial plaque was also unveiled in Moscow for [...]

the degenerate, and the pro-Ukrainian Zhvanetskiy. [...] And what exactly Zhvanetskiy did for Russia, is still not known. Probably, it's for his dream to level Russia to the ground. Or for calling Russian soldiers rapists and robbers" (Pod led, 6 March 2024). Other posts demand: "It's high time to apply cancel culture to all artists who became pro-Ukrainian after the start of the special military operation. Russophobia should be punishable. It's simple: books, films, paintings, and music with Russophobic and Christianophobic narratives should be banned in Russia" (Syny monarchii, 13 January 2025).

Social mobilization is beneficial for Putin's Russia because regime's narratives alone do not effectively mobilize people (Dalton 2023). Without pro-war hardliners, the Kremlin can depend on silent, acquiescent, apolitical citizens, but such population will not come out to support Putin if necessary. As the regime demands more sacrifices from the populace during wartime, it may need a support base that is more active and less apt to pose a threat to regime security. Creating such a base will likely be a challenge (Snegovaya, Kimmage, and McGlynn 2023). Also, Russia's strategy for victory in Ukraine involves extending the conflict into a "long war," necessitating a prolonged state of societal and elite mobilization against perceived domestic and external threats. The Kremlin seeks to transform passive wartime approval into at least "performative support" – if not active endorsement (Komin 2024).

Discussion – How Far Can Hardliners Go in Their Opposition to the Regime?

In selected TG channels' posts, there is a strong undercurrent of frustration with political and business elites accused of prioritizing personal interests over Russia's future or even colluding with the West. A recurring criticism is directed at military leadership, blamed not only for battlefield losses but also for a broader failure to adequately prepare for war. This critique runs deeper than military strategy, highlighting systemic flaws within the Russian state—bureaucracy, corruption, and a lack of strategic vision. The Russian elite is portrayed as undermining the war effort through incompetence or deliberate betrayal, with posts condemning their failure to mobilize the population and their lack of urgency in preparing the country for prolonged conflict.

Some of the more radical posts center on what they describe as "internal betrayal," targeting elites with financial ties to the West and depicting them as traitors playing both sides (Soldatskaya pravda, 14 August 2024). Russian oligarchs, bureaucrats, and military officers are frequently accused of sabotaging the war effort out of self-interest, corruption, or detachment from the war's realities (Govorit TopaZ, 4 June 2023). These individuals are portrayed as

indifferent to the suffering of Russian soldiers and citizens, more focused on preserving their wealth and influence than securing victory.

The term "khitroplanovtsy" (clever planners) appears in posts expressing fears that the war may end in a compromise viewed as unjust or detrimental to Russia's long-term interests (Soldatskaya pravda, 31 January 2025). This sense of betrayal extends beyond political elites to include anyone seen as too accommodating to the West or insufficiently committed to the war's ultimate goals. Some posts argue that the government is failing to rally the nation, instead "demobilizing" society—an error perceived as dangerous in the context of what is framed as an existential struggle (Soldatskaya pravda, 15 April 2024).

However, pro-war hardliners are rarely directing their anger at Putin himself. Notable exceptions included Prigozhin and Girkin, who did not question legitimacy of Putin's power or the idea of invading Ukraine but criticized him as weak and easily manipulated by foreign leaders or his entourage (Sochnev 2023). Girkin stated: "For 23 years, the country was led by a lowlife who managed to 'throw dust in the eyes' of a significant part of the population... The country will not endure another six years under this cowardly imbecile" (Strelkov Ivan Ivanovich, 18 July 2023). His unauthorized political activities and sharp criticism of regime officials on social media led to his arrest on extremism charges in July 2023. In January 2024, he was sentenced to four years in a penal colony, serving as a means for the regime to establish and enforce its "red lines."

Prigozhin's mutiny in June 2023, a culmination of Prigozhin's conflict with the Defense Ministry, highlighted that challenges to Putin's regime might arise from his own pro-war supporters (Turchenko 2023). Prigozhin framed his rebellion as a "march of justice" against the military establishment (Deutsche Welle 2023) Prigozhin's mutiny was not caused by ideological discords. It stemmed from a power struggle to save his Wagner Group from being absorbed by the Ministry of Defense after heavy losses in Bakhmut. Prigozhin clearly crossed the informal red lines set by the regime and despite reaching a deal with Putin negotiated by Lukashenka making him stop some 200 kilometers before Moscow, his death in a plane crash two months later raised questions about the circumstances. His rebellion was the first of its kind in Russia since the siege of the "White House" in October 1993 and, according to some commentators, a significant challenge to Putin's rule (Bailey, Wolkov, Hird, and Clark 2023).

Following the mutiny, pro-war hardliners split between moving past the rebellion and addressing the internal security flaws it exposed. Wagner-affiliated hardline influencers praised the peaceful end of the rebellion, while others condemned Prigozhin's actions, considering his demarche unacceptable in the conditions of war and provoking a civil war (Bailey, Wolkov,

Hird, and Clark 2023; Stanton 2023; Alperovich 2024a). Many pro-war hardliners criticized not only Prigozhin himself, but also the military and political leaders of the country, considering the mutiny as a result of their mistakes in leadership (Alperovich 2024a; Kholmogorov, 24 June 2023). Girkin stated that day that “in the current situation, every honest officer who remembers the Oath is obliged to confront the rebels. Regardless of how he feels about the current president, defense minister, etc.” (Strelkov Igor Ivanovich, 24 June 2023).

After accusing Prigozhin of treason, the Kremlin moved swiftly to dismantle his corporate empire (Sauer and Burke 2023). Despite this, Prigozhin refrained from criticizing Putin, even after the mutiny, as his grievances appeared to be primarily directed at Russia’s top military leadership rather than the president himself (Turchenko 2023). There is no public record of Prigozhin making negative statements about Putin following the rebellion. In fact, on July 10, 2023, the Kremlin announced that Prigozhin had met with Putin just five days after the mutiny and reaffirmed his loyalty to the regime (France 24, 2023).

The regime apparently fears any organized opposition, even loyalist and pro-war factions, and has blocked efforts by hardliners to organize politically or publicly. This fear, which has grown since Prigozhin’s mutiny in June 2023, also probably contributed to Girkin's arrest (OSW 2023). Girkin’s attempts to form a new organization and his large audience on Telegram made him a perceived threat. His arrest highlighted the regime's fear of grassroots movements, which it views as uncontrollable. The regime is likely to hinder pro-war hardliners from organizing. When the re-invasion of Ukraine began, pro-war hardliners were not even allowed to hold a rally (Verkhovskiy and Senshin 2024). While these hardliners maintain influence in the online sphere, they lack the capacity to mobilize as a political force on the streets. Post-Wagner military groups, such as Española, which recruit ultra-nationalists, are now under close regime control.

Pro-war hardliners who could have organized into armed militias with real combat power, experience, and autonomy from the regime no longer exist after Prigozhin's death, confirming that any degree of autonomy for such actors can be detrimental to the regime. Putin’s regime is focused on maintaining security and predictability and any autonomous movement, even if it is in support of the regime today, may disagree on something tomorrow. The authorities likely began to view the pro-war hardliners as the only remaining group with the potential to inspire social discontent. A part of the regime’s social base may be receptive to more radical slogans. However, the weak response of the hardliners to Girkin’s arrest and Prigozhin’s death proves that their potential has been effectively neutralized for the moment (OSW 2023).

Prigozhin's death and Girkin's imprisonment did not mean that pro-war hardliners were marginalized, they just lost potential leaders, but it did not lose much in online popularity (see Table 1). The regime succeeded in its efforts to prevent the hardliners to have their own leader with wider popularity. However, pro-war hardliners could pose a problem in the future in case of Russia's defeats. On the other hand, even despite potential efforts to mobilize, Russian society is rather politically inactive and the mass protest of hardliners on the streets of Russian cities looks like a chimerical threat: according to various estimates only about 5% of Russians - the most ardent hardliners - are willing to take to the streets without resigning themselves to Russia's military defeat or a truce with Ukraine considered unfavorable (Kravchenko 2023). The Kremlin's actions against Girkin and Prigozhin signal that criticism of the authorities should be limited, though the exact boundaries still remain unclear and are determined by the regime's shifting *'ponyatiya'* (Verkhovskiy 2023).

Prigozhin's and Girkin's fates demonstrate the reality and elasticity of these red lines. The regime prefers hardliners to be disorganized and without a recognized leader, making them easier to control and prone to internal conflicts. While no open attacks against Putin are currently seen on hardliners' TG channels, it's unclear if this is due to the elimination of critical leaders or other factors like fear of repression or genuine support for Putin.

Ethnic xenophobia expressed by almost all pro-war hardliners on social media, not only those that have been selected for this paper, could become a future red line, but so far there are no signs that such red lines have been set by the regime despite harsh criticism (Alperovich 2024b). Russian government is criticized by these hardliners for allegedly facilitating the replacement of Russian nationals with migrants, which is portrayed as a betrayal of the Russian people and their heritage and the deliberate erosion of Russia's cultural identity. This is tied to a broader sense of cultural displacement and fears of demographic collapse, which have been exacerbated by the ongoing conflict (Soldatskaya pravda, 14 August 2024; Ryadovoi Gubarev, 23 January 2025).

Conclusion

Empirical findings in this paper demonstrate that, despite their criticism of the regime and its officials (excluding Putin), ultra-nationalist hardliners are beneficial to the regime as pro-war influencers. These hardliners, while critical, help disseminate and amplify the regime's core messages, particularly regarding the war against Ukraine. Pro-war hardliners function as echo chambers within the pro-war segment of society that remains skeptical of state propaganda,

redirecting their frustrations toward shared enemies of Putin's regime. They provide alternative platforms for pro-war sentiment to circulate in Russia's online public sphere, which, unlike state-monopolized television, allows for some degree of pluralism. Their endorsement of the war reinforces the regime's legitimacy and serves to justify both foreign policy decisions and domestic repression of anti-war dissent.

The public prominence of these hardliners enables the regime to cite them as evidence of widespread, zealous support for the war and for domestic crackdowns, portraying such measures as aligned with the will of the Russian people. As low-cost assets and conditional proxies, they help rationalize the war, framing it as not only necessary but also inevitable and existential—not just for Putin's rule but for Russia's greatness, survival, and imperial identity. Unlike the outspoken anti-regime political opposition, pro-war hardliners do not challenge the regime's foundations. Instead, they push for more decisive and violent actions, advocating for even more committed militaristic society, where everything is subordinated to the war effort, including all aspects of Russian citizens' private lives.

The regime can rely on hardliners as allies against any potential disruptions to Russia's war efforts due to external or internal reasons. A crucial factor for the regime is allowing tacit support or some autonomy for the online activities of pro-war hardliners, as they have no leader or organization. However, the influence of pro-war hardliners remains largely confined to the online public sphere. The regime is wary of any unsanctioned public activities, even those that express loyalty and align with its ideology. To prevent their radicalization from spiraling beyond its control, the regime informally regulates them by establishing red lines. Pro-war hardliners remain relevant in Russia's public discourse as influencers who reinforce and amplify pro-war narratives, particularly among the actively pro-war segment that distrusts official propaganda and the younger social media audience.

Prigozhin's mutiny and Girkin's jailing did not significantly change the rhetoric of pro-war hardliners. They remain active online, avoiding unsanctioned activism—a tangible red line set by the regime—and refraining from direct criticism of Putin. Instead, they harshly criticize individual regime officials, army generals, or oligarchs, and promote ethnic xenophobia, which may become a future red line within the shifting boundaries of '*ponyatiya*,' the informal rules governing interactions within the regime and between the regime and outsiders. While these hardliners support the regime's legitimacy and the war against Ukraine, the regime's reluctance to allow their organization underscores its apprehension of unsanctioned movements.

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